

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02 | TYPE OF ACTION: CSA | GA n. 101079148

D.5.7 E-RIHS ERIC User Strategy: Approach and Advancement

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ABSTRACT

This report presents the approach by which an updated User Strategy for E-RIHS will be developed, and details progress towards this goal, together with an action plan of key steps that will be implemented between July and May 2024. The *User and Access Policy*, developed during the preparatory phase of E-RIHS PP is the foundation for the updated User Strategy, and will be re-drafted to ensure alignment between the needs of E-RIHS users and the technical capabilities of national facilities. The User Strategy is intended to be a forward-looking document that will consider both current and potential future users and will outline necessary information gathering processes for the assessment of current and prospective user needs, as well as indicating pathways by which this information can be used within E-RIHS decision-making processes. The development of the strategy will pay close attention to the progression of corresponding parallel tasks concerning users in other E-RIHS IP work packages.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project number	101079148	Acronym	E-RIHS IP
Full title	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science – Implementation Phase		
Project url	www.e-rihs.eu		
Document url			
EU Project Officer	Emiliano CAROZZA		

Deliverable	Number	D5.7	Title	E-RIHS ERIC User Strategy: Approach and Advancement
Work Package	Number	WP 5	Title	Access and digital services of E-RIHS

Deliverable nature	Report		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	(31/07/2023)		
Actual delivery date	(31/07/2023)		
Status	Version 3	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

Lead Partners(s)	19/ICCROM		
Authors (Partner)	19/ICCROM		
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Total number of pages	16
Keywords	E-RIHS: Heritage Science; User Strategy

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
29/06/2023	1	A. Heritage	Initial version
	2	iCNN	Updated version according to the iCNN member inputs.
31/07/2023	3	A. Heritage, G. Lazzeri and V. Virgili	General revision and editing

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ABBREVIATIONS

ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
HS	Heritage Science
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
WP	Workpackage
T	Task
iCNN	(interim)Committee of National Nodes of E-RIHS
IKC	In-Kind Contribution

INTRODUCTION

Task Description (from the E-RIHS IP Grant Agreement):

Task 5.5: Updating and upgrading the user strategy (M4-M20) – Lead ICCROM, participants: ATOMKI, FSP, HERCULES, KIK-IRPA, NCU, NG-UCL, UL-ZVKDS, UM, ZVKDS.

The main goal is to upgrade the E-RIHS User Strategy to ensure alignment among the needs of E-RIHS users and the technical capabilities of national facilities. A broad coverage of diverse user communities will be reached by an effective interaction with the wide HS communities via the #HSAcademy representing the E-RIHS users' forum. The #HSAcademy is a virtual interdisciplinary HS research environment, a vivid forum to enable communication, collaboration and exchange among experts, internal and external E-RIHS researchers. Role of partners: This task is led by ICCROM, with support of ATOMKI, FSP, HERCULES, KIK-IRPA, NCU, NG-UCL, UL-ZVKDS, UM, and ZVKDS.

Deliverable: D5.5 E-RIHS ERIC User Strategy (M20; ICCROM; R; PU)

DEVELOPMENT OF THE APPROACH TO THE TASK

Discussions have been held during the regular weekly meetings of Task WP5, to define the purpose and scope of the user strategy together with other E-RIHS IP Project partners. Additionally, a side meeting was organized at the first interim project meeting in Krakow (5-7 June 2023) with partners from Workpackages 1,2,3 and 4 to discuss the User Strategy scope and purpose, and ways to ensure the strategy is well aligned with the work of the other workpackges within E-RIHS IP.

From these discussions the following key points have emerged:

- The User Strategy should be forward looking, setting out E-RIHS ERIC aspirations for how it seeks to improve its service to current users, and reach out to a wider diversity of new users in the future.
- The strategy should differentiate between existing and potential new user communities
- For existing user communities:
 - the strategy should provide a roadmap for assessing user needs and their level of satisfaction regarding E-RIHS services.
- For potential new user communities:
 - The strategy should indicate pathways through which to reach and engage new users, and assess their needs
- The strategy should set out how information received from user surveys can be incorporated within E-RIHS decision making processes, so that E-RIHS can continue to develop as a learning organisation and meet the evolving needs of its users.

- The User strategy needs to be closely aligned with the work of other workpackages in E-RIHS IP, in particular: WP2 T2.4 Rules of Procedure – concerning User Representation; WP4 T4.2 Enlargement strategy; T4.3 HS Academy; and WP3 T3.4 E-RIHS KPIs.
- The User strategy should be viewed as a living document and will need to be periodically revised and updated.

ADVANCEMENT OF THE TASK

1. Collection of existing User Strategy documents (E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS)

The following strategy documents developed during the E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS projects have been collected for review:

E-RIHS PP

- D.5.1 User strategy and access policies (https://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D5.1_User-strategy-and-access-policies.pdf)
- D.9.2 Analysis of innovation background (https://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/D_9_2_INNOVATION_V1_HQ-1.pdf)

IPERION HS

- D.7.1 IPERION HS Training plan
- D7.2 Detailed engagement plan for new users' communities
<https://zenodo.org/record/5788564>
- D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy
<https://zenodo.org/record/5788566>

Forthcoming IPERION HS

- D7.6 Report on engagement with user communities and on user research needs
- D6.5 Agenda for SMART innovation

2. Review of strategy documents available through the websites of EU ERICS

Strategy documents made available via the websites of other EU ERICS (those listed at: <https://www.eric-forum.eu/the-eric-landscape/>) have been reviewed to identify comparative materials that may prove useful for developing the User Strategy. Of these, the following ERICS in particular afforded useful comparison material: BBMRI; CLARIN; EATRIS; EMSO; and ECOS (see Appendix II).

3. Collation of existing User Data

Data collected by the E-RIHS IP project and also during the IPERION HS project concerning users has been collated. Data from ongoing surveys (IPERION HS D6.5 Gap analysis survey) will also be added.

This data comprises:

- IPERION-HS User reports (from Archlab; Molab; and Fixlab platforms)
- IPERION HS User satisfaction survey (conducted July 2021-April 2023 across Archlab; Molab; and Fixlab platforms; 53 respondents)
- IPERION HS Service requests

- IPERION HS User statistics: academic backgrounds & keywords for research interests

4. Outline Strategy Document

A draft outline of the user strategy document has been drafted, and shared via Teams with all partners for consideration (see Appendix I).

The draft includes the following aspects:

1. Appraisal of the current situation (Where we stand)

- Who are E-RIHS users and what are their needs?
- What services are available, and how well are they accessed?
- How satisfied are users with the service provision?
- What future improvements are planned?

2. Future Outlook (Where we want to go)

Exploiting E-RIHS capacities to address unmet heritage science needs

- How can user needs, experiences and outcomes be better assessed?
- How can services be improved?

Engaging new research communities to advance heritage science

- Who might be E-RIHS users in the future, and how can they be reached?
- What will be their needs, and how can these be met?

Empowering the heritage science community through training

- What future training needs might users have, and how can these be met?

3. Strategy for Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (How we will get there)

- Gathering information on users' perspectives
- Developing E-RIHS services
- Evolving the E-RIHS user base

PLAN OF ACTION (TIMELINE)

In the coming months (M10-20) the following activities will be undertaken:

1. What is the current user strategy?

Review of existing strategy documents from E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS to identify key components for integration into the new user strategy (ongoing - SEPTEMBER 2023).

2. Who are the current users and what are their needs?

Review of user data available through the IPERION HS and E-RIHS IP projects to provide an overview of the current situation with regard to user profiles and needs (ongoing-SEPTEMBER 2023)

3. How is user feedback currently obtained?

Map user consultation pathways and review existing user survey forms employed within IPERION HS project: to inform the development of the MEL system proposed as part of the user strategy. (ongoing – SEPTEMBER 2023)

4. How does the access process work at present?

Map user access pathways – together with providers and users, to capture and evaluate the processes through which users access services and how the research process develops through their delivery, to identify where potential gaps and opportunities may lie (to be done in WP5 – T5.1). (starting SEPTEMBER 2023)

5. How are new users reached?

Starting from the IPERION HS *engagement plan for new users' communities* (deliverables 7.1-7.6): map current activities to engage users also via the HS Academy, through consultation with service providers and HS Academy coordinators. Relevant user associations at national and international level will also be mapped (starting SEPTEMBER 2023)

6. What is our future vision for E-RIHS?

SWOT analysis of current service provision and visioning exercise to define a shared future outlook for the E-RIHS user strategy. This will be conducted as an online workshop, engaging both E-RIHS service providers, users and other key stakeholders. To ensure sufficient diversity, participants will be selected from suggestions given by E-RIHS national coordinators, and other key community groups (eg partners of the EU CSA action ARCHE) (NOVEMBER 2023)

7. Interviews with platform coordinators and other key stakeholders to deepen the findings of the SWOT and visioning workshop (if needed, JANUARY 2024)

8. Integrating the user strategy work within E-RIHS IP

Liaison with other WP leaders, to ensure alignment with other E-RIHS IP tasks and deliverables (throughout, but with a focus meeting FEBRUARY 2024)

9. Drafting the user strategy (MARCH 2024)

10. Review by partners (APRIL 2024)

11. Finalisation of the User Strategy (MAY 2024 = M20)

T1.1: GANTT of the Plan of Action

TASK	2023						2024				
	July (M10)	Aug (M11)	Sep (M12)	Oct (M13)	Nov (M14)	Dec (M15)	Jan (M16)	Feb (M17)	Mar (M18)	Apr (M19)	May (M20)
Review user data	█	█	█								
Review consultation processes	█	█	█								
Review strategy documents	█	█	█								
Map user access pathways*	█	█	█								
Map user engagement activities & associations			█	█	█						
Online workshop (SWOT, visioning)					█						
Interviews (if needed)							█				
Liaison with other E-RIHS IP WPs	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Drafting the User Strategy									█		
Review by partners										█	
Finalisation of the user strategy											█*

* D5.8 E-RIHS ERIC User Strategy

APPENDIX I – OUTLINE DRAFT OF THE E-RIHS USER STRATEGY

SECTION 1: Introduction

1.1 AIM AND PURPOSE

Sets out the aim and intended purpose of the document

1.2 SCOPE

Sets out the scope of the document

1.3 BACKGROUND

This section provides an introductory background as to why an updated User Strategy for E-RIHS is needed, referencing previous user strategy documents (E-RIHS user strategy, and also documents developed through IPERION HS).

SECTION 2: Where we stand

2.1 E-RIHS USERS AND THEIR NEEDS

Describes the current user base of E-RIHS, and the types of services that are requested, drawing on data gathered through the IPERION HS project, and through E-RIHS IP project.

- Description of current users
- Description of current service requests

2.2 SERVICES PROVIDED

Provides an overview of the current service offer and access pathways, and how these are currently functioning, drawing on data gathered through the IPERION HS project, and through E-RIHS IP. The section should also highlight the main outcomes of work within the E-RIHS IP project to improve these aspects (e.g. catalogue of services).

- Description of current services and access modalities
- Description of current service evaluation

2.3 USER SATISFACTION

Sets out findings of previous surveys regarding current user satisfaction with service offer and access pathways

2.4 PLANNED FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

Summarises planned improvements to the catalogue of services developed through E-RIHS IP

- Proposed improvements through E-RIHS IP

SECTION 3: Where we want to go

Sets out a user-centred vision for the evolution of E-RIHS's services and user base, and how this might be achieved. Outlines key pathways for gathering information on user needs and experiences and how this can be used to improve and evolve E-RIHS services. Also considers how new users might be

reached and engaged, drawing on work undertaken with E-RIHS IP project concerning the HS Academy, and what future training needs they might have.

3.1: EXPLOITING E-RIHS CAPACITIES TO ADDRESS UNMET HERITAGE SCIENCE NEEDS

- How can user needs, experiences and outcomes be better assessed?
- How can services be improved?

3.2: ENGAGING NEW RESEARCH COMMUNITIES TO ADVANCE HERITAGE SCIENCE

- Who might be E-RIHS users in the future, and how can they be reached?
- What will be their needs, and how can these be met?

3.3: EMPOWERING THE HERITAGE SCIENCE COMMUNITY THROUGH TRAINING

- What future training needs might users have, and how can these be met?

SECTION 4: Strategy for monitoring, evaluation and development

This section sets out a strategy to achieve the vision detailed above. It describes the pathways for gathering information regarding user needs and experiences to improve and evolve E-RIHS services, and how this information will be used in E-RIHS decision making, to inform future development of the E-RIHS ERIC

4.1 GATHERING INFORMATION ON USERS' PERSPECTIVES

Sets out the processes through which users can be consulted regarding their needs, experience of, and outcomes derived through E-RIHS services, drawing on existing pathways already established within IPERION HS, and those proposed through the E-RIHS IP project, integrating these within the service platforms and E-RIHS HS Academy. A summary table will identify target audiences, scheduling and responsible entities for undertaking the consultations (consultation plan).

- Needs assessments (gap analysis)
- Outcomes evaluation
- Consultation plan

4.2 DEVELOPMENT OF E-RIHS SERVICES

Set out the processes through which learning gained through user consultations might be incorporated into future design of services, considering E-RIHS governance and decision-making structures.

- User representation in the Committee of National Nodes

4.3 EVOLUTION OF THE E-RIHS USER BASE

Describes the ways through which E-RIHS can reach potential new users and gain feedback concerning their service needs, through national nodes and the E-RIHS HS Academy, as well as through liaison with external user organisations and community groups. Will also outline future community building activities for new users to strengthen engagement and knowledge exchange. Within the strategy, user communities in non-E-RIHS and non-EU member states will be considered (in line with the E-RIHS enlargement plan - T4.2), as well as users from CCS and the private sector.

- User outreach through E-RIHS national nodes
- User outreach through the HS Academy

- User outreach through external user organisations and community groups
- Users from external member states (including non–EU countries)
- Community building activities for new users

SECTION 5: End matter

DEFINITIONS

Provides definitions for key terms and acronyms used within the document

REFERENCES

List of references cited within the document

VERSIONING

The user strategy is a living document, and will need to be periodically updated. The current version of the document is detailed here, with a description of key amendments made to the previous versions.

APPENDIX II - REVIEW OF STRATEGY DOCUMENTS AVAILABLE THROUGH THE WEBSITES OF EU ERICS

BBMRI-ERIC	BBMRI is a European Research Infrastructure for biobanking that brings together all the main players from the biobanking field – researchers, biobankers, industry, and patients – to boost biomedical research. (Project coordinator).
Comment: See web section on Stakeholder Forum: https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/stakeholder-forum/	
CERIC-ERIC	CERIC (Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium) is a Research Infrastructure that provides open access to some of the best facilities in Europe, to help science and industry advance in all fields of materials, biomaterials and nanotechnology.
Comment: Little information regarding a user strategy, apart from comments in STD: https://www.ceric-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Technical_Scientific_Document.pdf	
CESSDA-ERIC	CESSDA, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the Social Sciences.
Comment: Strategy document. Presents a SWOT, and stakeholder analysis. But no user strategy	
CLARIN-ERIC	CLARIN, Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure, makes digital language resources available to scholars, researchers, students and citizen-scientists from all disciplines, especially in humanities and Social Sciences through single sign-on access.
Comment: the structure of CLARIN includes a <u>User Involvement Committee</u> : <i>User Involvement Committee</i> <i>The User Involvement Committee (UIC) is a committee that reports to the Board of Directors. Its main responsibility is to facilitate and promote the CLARIN</i> <i>User Involvement activities, such as surveys, reports, financing instruments and outreach. Its main tasks include:</i> <i>facilitating the UI initiatives conducted by CLARIN ERIC</i> <i>promoting the UI financing instruments within their consortium and networks of researchers</i> <i>promoting UI participation at the relevant national and international UI events</i> <i>facilitating the UI surveys conducted by CLARIN ERIC</i> Webpage Strategy sections and also strategy document section on Knowledge Infrastructure (https://www.clarin.eu/content/vision-and-strategy) also contain useful comparative material.	
DARIAH-ERIC	DARIAH, the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, is a pan-European infrastructure for arts and humanities scholars working with computational methods. It supports digital research as well as the teaching of digital research methods.
Comment: Although no 'user strategy' available on the webpages, some useful statements set out in the Strategic plan: https://www.dariah.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Strategic-Plan_2019-2026.pdf	
EATRIS-ERIC	EATRIS is a European infrastructure for translational medicine that plays a fundamental role in the advancement of knowledge and technology in translational research and drug development.
Comment: No 'User Strategy', but users are a main focus of the Strategic Plan (see in particular comments on communities of practice), which could serve as a good model: https://eatris.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Strategic-Plan-2023%E2%80%932026_fin.pdf The process for developing the strategic plan is also set out.	
ECRIN-ERIC	ECRIN, the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network, links scientific partners and networks across Europe to facilitate multinational Clinical Research.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	

ECCSEL-ERIC	ECCSEL, the European Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage Laboratory Infrastructure, provides researchers across the globe easy access to its facilities and coordinates facility upgrades and new builds.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
EMSO ERIC	EMSO, the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory, aims to explore the oceans, to gain a better understanding of phenomena happening within and below them, and to explain the critical role that these phenomena play in the broader Earth systems.
Comment: See strategic plan pg. 15: <i>EMSO ERIC DRIVEN BY USER NEEDS</i> https://emso.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/EMSO_ERIC_STRATEGIC_PLAN_2021-23.pdf	
European Social Survey	The European Social Survey is an academically driven cross-national survey that measures the attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns of diverse populations in more than thirty nations.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
Euro-Argo ERIC	Euro-Argo ERIC is the Research Infrastructure coordinating and strengthening of the European contribution to the international Argo programme. Its mission is to achieve the objectives of the OneArgo global ocean monitoring system in order to better understand and predict the ocean, its role in the climate system and its health.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
European Spallation Source ERIC	The European Spallation Source is a joint European organisation committed to building and operating the world's leading facility for research using neutrons.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
ICOS	ICOS, the Integrated Carbon Observation System, is a RI which provides harmonised and high-precision scientific data on carbon cycle and greenhouse gas budget and perturbations.
Comment: See strategy document: https://www.icos-cp.eu/sites/default/files/cmisis/ICOS%20Strategy.pdf In particular pages 28-33	
JIV-ERIC	JIVE, the Joint Institute for VLBI, is an international astronomy institute that provides support for users of the European VLBI Network (EVN).
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
Instruct-ERIC	Instruct is a Pan-European Research Infrastructure in structural biology, making high-end technologies and methods available to all European researchers.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
LifeWatch.ERIC	LifeWatch provides e-Science research facilities to scientists seeking to increase knowledge and deepen understanding of Biodiversity organisation and Ecosystem functions and services.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
SHARE-ERIC	SHARE is a multidisciplinary & cross-national panel database of micro data on health, socio-economic status & social & family networks of more than 120000 individuals.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
InfraFrontiere	InfraFrontier is a Research Infrastructure that provides access to mouse models, data, and scientific platforms and services to study the functional role of the genome in human health and disease.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
Euro-Biolmaging ERIC	Euro-Biolmaging is a research infrastructure that offers open access to imaging technologies, training and data services in biological and biomedical imaging.

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Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
EMBRC-ERIC	EMBRC, the European Marine Biological Resource Centre, is a Research infrastructure responding to the societal Grand Challenges through advanced marine biology and ecology research.
Comment: Science strategy available on webpages – but with little mention of users or stakeholders	
EU-OPENSREEN ERIC	EU-OPENSREEN, the European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology, supporting life science research and its translation to medicine and agriculture.
Comment: Good representation of users on the website, with a section dedicated to user stories. But no user strategy information or strategic plan available on webpages	
ELI ERIC	ELI, the Extreme Light Infrastructure, is the world’s most advanced international laser research infrastructure. It is a multi-site infrastructure with three complementary facilities in the Czech Republic, Hungary and Romania.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	
EPOS ERIC	EPOS, the European Plate Observing System, is a long-term plan to facilitate integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from distributed research infrastructures for solid Earth science in Europe.
Comment: User strategy information/strategic plan not available on webpages	